

MARS STANDS IN 7TH BHAVA IN SHADOW PLANET'S STARS AND DELAY MARRIAGE

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Abstract:

Mars is called as Mangala karagan. If Mars gets positive strength in horoscope the marriage never delay. If Mars gets negative strength in horoscope the marriage always delay. Positive strength means Mars is located in Lagna/third/fifth / sixth/ ninth/tenth or eleventh bhava. Negative strength means Mars is located in second/fourth/seventh/eighth or twelveth bhava. This rule is common for male and female. rasi chart. D1 indicates the strength of Mars.

Key Words: Mars - Standing Bhavas - Second - Fourth - Seventh - Eighth - Twelveth - Late Marriage - Rasi Chart - Mars Dhosha - Example Horoscopes - Rules Exceptions - Shadow Planets - Rahu - Kethu.

What is Mars Dhosha?

If Mars Stands in Second, fourth, seventh, eighth or twelveth bhava from lagna or moon sign or from Venus. It is called Mars dhosha or Mangal dhosha. It gets great place in marriage matching. We should match the above horoscope with one whose Mars is located in second, fourth, seventh, eighth or twelveth bhava. Thus we match the horoscopes for marriage. Otherwise the separation will be possible.

Mars Dhosha Exceptions:

There are some exceptions have seen in the ancient books.

According to Prasanna Markam Book:

- If Mars occupies its exhalation house capricorn there is no Mars dhosha
- If Mars occupies its friendly house sagittarius and pisces there is no Mars dhosha.

There are some exceptions have seen in the ancient book, "Jathaga Saaram".

According to Jathaga Saaram Book:

Whose ascendent is Aries, Scorpio, Taurus, Libra, Gemini, Virgo Capricorn, Cancer, Leo, Sagittarius and Pisces there is no Mars dhosha. From this we know whose ascendent is Aquaris and also Mars stands in 1/2/4/7/8/12 bhavas the native has Mars dhosha.

According to Palitha Marthandam Book:

According to Palitha Marthandam, who born in movable ascendent like Aries, Cancer, Libra there is no Mars dhosha, Mars stands in any bhava.

According to Jathaga Marthandam Book:

According to Jathaga Marthandam if Mars occupies the houses of Mercury, Gemini and Virgo there is no Mars dhosha.

What will Mars do in 1/2/4/7/8/12:

Mars in Lagna: Lagna indicates one's health. Lagna is seventh house from seventh house. It is maraga stana for spouse. It indicates the death of spouse. So, Mars in lagna bhava indicates dhosha.

Mars in 2 (Family Bhava): Second bhava indicates pleasure in family life. Second house is eighth house from seventh house. It indicates the dangers of spouse. So, Mars in Second bhava indicates dhosha.

Mars in 4 (Property Bhava): Fourth bhava indicates, mother, land, home, vehicle, Fourth bhava destroys 1/5/9 triangle. So, the natives health and properties are affected. So, Mars in fourth bhava indicates dhosha.

Mars in 7 (Kalasthira Bhava): Seventh bhava indicates the relationship between the native and the spouse. It also indicates the unity of spouse. So, Mars in Seventh bhava is dhosha.

Mars in 8 (Mangalya Bhava): Eighth bhava indicates the life span of the couple. So, Mars in eighth bhava is dhosha.

Mars in 12 (Ayana Sayana Bhava): Twelveth bhava indicates the sexual intercourse in bed and also loss. So Mars in twelveth bhava is dhosha.

Rules for Late Marriage:

We have seen three rules with example which cause late marriage due to Mars stands in Seventh bhava.

Rule 1: Mars stands in seventh bhava in the star of Rahu, the natives marriage would be delay.

Example Chart 1.1

Gender : Male
 Date of birth : 05.08.1982
 Time of birth : 11.34 pm
 Place of birth : Tirunelveli
 Birth Star : Danishta
 Ascendent : Aries
 Balance Dasa : Mars dasa 04 yrs 03 months 09 days

12	ASC	2	Rahu Venus	Rahu	Mercury	Venus	11
11	Rasi		Sun	7	Navamsa		12
Moon			Mercury	6			Saturn ASC
Kethu	8	Mars Jupiter	Saturn	Sun Jupiter Mars	4	3	Kethu Moon

Planet	Degree	Star	Patha
Lagna	13 ⁰ 59'	Bharani	1
Sun	19 ⁰ 22'	Ayilyam	1
Moon	28 ⁰ 31'	Danishta	2
Mars	07 ⁰ 41'	Swathi	1
Mercury	01 ⁰ 14'	Magam	1
Jupiter	08 ⁰ 59'	Swathi	1
Venus	25 ⁰ 47'	Punarvasu	2
Saturn	23 ⁰ 44'	Chitra	1
Rahu	18 ⁰ 05'	Arudra	4
Kethu	18 ⁰ 05'	Pooradam	2

In this horoscope Mars stands in Seventh bhava in Swathi, the star of Rahu (Shadow planet). So, he got married at the age of 37

Example Chart 1.2:

Gender : Male
 Date of birth : 30.01.1983
 Time of birth : 7.34 pm
 Place of birth : Tanjore
 Birth Star : Magam 3
 Ascendent : Leo
 Balance Dasa : Kethu dasa 01 yr 10 months 09 days

8	9	10	Rahu	11	12	ASC Sun	Kethu Moon
Mars Venus	Rasi		12	Mars	Navamsa		3
Sun			ASC Moon	Saturn			4
Mercury Kethu	Jupiter	Saturn	2	Rahu Venus	Mercury	Jupiter	5

Planet	Degree	Star	Patha
Lagna	04 ⁰ 24'	Magam	2
Sun	16 ⁰ 29'	Sravanam	2
Moon	09 ⁰ 49'	Magam	3
Mars	16 ⁰ 36'	Sathayam	3
Mercury	23 ⁰ 25'	Pooradam	3
Jupiter	12 ⁰ 44'	Anuradha	3
Venus	07 ⁰ 27'	Sathayam	1
Saturn	10 ⁰ 40'	Swathi	2
Rahu	08 ⁰ 40'	Arudra	1
Kethu	08 ⁰ 40'	Moolam	3

In this horoscope Mars stands in Seventh bhava in Sathayam, the star of Rahu (Shadow Planet). The native got married at the age of 37.

Rule 2: Mars stands in seventh bhava in the star of Kethu, the natives marriage would be late.

Example Chart 1.3:

Gender : Male
 Date of birth : 10.04.1976
 Time of birth : 10.51 pm
 Place of birth : Pattukottai
 Birth Star : Magam 2
 Ascendent : Sagittarius
 Balance Dasa : Kethu dasa 04 yrs 06 months 05 days

Sun Venus	Mercury Jupiter Kethu	6	Mars
3	Rasi		Saturn
2			Moon
ASC	12	Rahu	10

Sun Mars	ASC Rahu	Moon	Mercury
11	Navamsa		Jupiter Saturn
10			5
9	8	Kethu	Venus

Planet	Degree	Star	Patha
Lagna	00 ⁰ 05'	Moolam	1
Sun	27 ⁰ 26'	Revathi	4
Moon	04 ⁰ 43'	Magam	2
Mars	17 ⁰ 25'	Arudra	4
Mercury	07 ⁰ 08'	Aswini	3
Jupiter	10 ⁰ 02'	Aswini	4
Venus	09 ⁰ 22'	Uthratathi	2
Saturn	02 ⁰ 40'	Punarvasu	4
Rahu	20 ⁰ 24'	Visagam	1
Kethu	20 ⁰ 24'	Bharani	3

In this horoscope Mars stands in Seventh bhava in Arudra, the star of Rahu (Shadow Planet). The native got married at the age of 41.

Rule 2: Mars stands in seventh bhava in the star of Kethu, the natives marriage would be delay.

Example Chart 2.1:

Gender : Female
 Date of birth : 30.01.1989
 Time of birth : 11.51 pm
 Place of birth : Trichy
 Birth Star : Visagam
 Ascendent : Libra
 Balance Dasa : Jupiter dasa 10 yrs 03 months 04 days.

6	Mars	Jupiter	9
5	Rasi		10
Sun Venus Mercury			Moon Kethu
Saturn	2	ASC Moon	12

4	5	Moon	Sun
Mercury	Navamsa		Kethu Mars
Jupiter Rahu Venus			Saturn
ASC	12	11	10

Planet	Degree	Star	Patha
Lagna	09 ⁰ 27'	Swathi	1
Sun	17 ⁰ 08'	Sravanam	3
Moon	24 ⁰ 46'	Visagam	2
Mars	12 ⁰ 45'	Aswini	4
Mercury	04 ⁰ 47'	Uthradam	3
Jupiter	02 ⁰ 34'	Karthiga	2
Venus	01 ⁰ 20'	Uthradam	2
Saturn	15 ⁰ 16'	Pooradam	1

Rahu	12 ⁰ 30'	Sathayam	2
Kethu	12 ⁰ 30'	Magam	4

In this horoscope Mars stands in Seventh bhava in Aswini, the star of Kethu (Shadow Planet) indicates the late of marriage. The native got married at the age of 35.

Example Chart 2.2:

Gender : Female
 Date of birth : 01.11.1981
 Time of birth : 2.51 pm
 Place of birth : Kodumodi
 Birth Star : Moolam 2
 Ascendent : Aquaris
 Balance Dasa : Kethu dasa 04 yrs 06 months 07 days

2	3	4	5
ASC	Rasi		Rahu
Kethu			Mars
Moon Venus	10	Jupiter Sun	Saturn

12	ASC Venus	Moon	3
Sun	Navamsa		Saturn Rahu Mars
Kethu			5
9	8	Jupiter	Mercury

Planet	Degree	Star	Patha
Lagna	22 ⁰ 59'	Pooratathi	1
Sun	15 ⁰ 16'	Swathi	3
Moon	04 ⁰ 43'	Moolam	2
Mars	12 ⁰ 55'	Magam	4
Mercury	26 ⁰ 48'	Chitra	2
Jupiter	01 ⁰ 05'	Chitra	3
Venus	02 ⁰ 04'	Moolam	1
Saturn	22 ⁰ 24'	Hastham	4
Rahu	02 ⁰ 47'	Punarvasu	4
Kethu	02 ⁰ 47'	Uthradam	2

In this horoscope Mars stands in Seventh in bhava Magam, the star of Kethu (Shadow Planet), the native got married at the age of 36.

Example Chart 2.3:

Gender : Male
 Date of birth : 19.01.1975
 Time of birth : 5.30 pm
 Place of birth : Erode
 Birth Star : Revathi 2
 Ascendent : Gemini
 Balance Dasa : Mercury dasa 09 yrs 06 months 22 days.

Moon	11	Kethu	Saturn (R) ASC
Jupiter			2
Venus Mercury Sun	Rasi		3
Mars	Rahu	5	4

11	Saturn (R) Jupiter	Kethu Mars ASC	2
Sun	Navamsa		Mercury Venus
Moon			4
8	Rahu	6	5

Planet	Degree	Star	Patha
Lagna	24 ⁰ 57'	Punarvasu	2
Sun	05 ⁰ 16'	Uthrada	3
Moon	22 ⁰ 30'	Revathi	2
Mars	04 ⁰ 49'	Moolam	2
Mercury	22 ⁰ 58'	Sravanam	4
Jupiter	23 ⁰ 13'	Pooratathi	1

Venus	23 ⁰ 01'	Sravanam	4
Saturn	20 ⁰ 50'	Punarvasu	1
Rahu	14 ⁰ 06'	Anuradha	4
Kethu	14 ⁰ 06'	Rohini	2

In this horoscope Mars stands in Seventh bhava in Moolam, the star of Kethu (Shadow Planet), the native got married at the age of 41.

Conclusion:

In so many horoscopes Mars stands at 7th house in the star of shadow planets (rahu & kethu) is the barrier for marriage. The remedy for this is to worship Lord Murugar in Pazhani or Tiruchendur on Tuesday at Abijith Muhurtham (11.45 am to 12.15 pm). It removes all the evil effects of Mars and purify the horoscope. So, Mars dosha people must worship Lord Murugar in Pazhani or Tiruchendur.

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